

Optimal operation of a pilot plant for CO₂-absorption of flue gas from a power plant

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Introduction

With a prospect to the political demand on lowering the emission of greenhouse gases the industry is forced to improve the technology to meet these standards. Therefore it is believed that CO₂ absorption will be of great importance in the future. The technology is still young and a lot of development needs to be done to make it cost-effective.

In this work we present data for absorption of CO₂ with monoethanolamine (MEA) in pilot plant at a numerous operation conditions. The data are moreover compared with a mathematical model.

Challenges

- Better understanding of the mechanism and kinetics.
- Improve the analysis method of CO₂ in alkanolamine.
- Fit the model to the specific column and compare with experiments.
- Operate the plant at different operation conditions.

Analysis method

The barium chloride method is based on precipitating carbonate and subsequently dissolve it again to remove the CO₂. By calculation the remaining HCl it is possible to determine the loading:

$$\text{wt}\% = \frac{C_{\text{HCl}}V_{\text{HCl}} - C_{\text{NaOH}}V_{\text{NaOH}}}{2m_{\text{sample}}}$$

$$\text{CO}_2\text{-loading} = \frac{\text{wt}\%_{\text{CO}_2} M_{\text{MEA}}}{\text{wt}\%_{\text{MEA}} M_{\text{CO}_2}}$$

Fig. 1. Determine the endpoint for titration. The theoretical value is a standard solution.

Fig. 1 shows how much CO₂ that is being recovered from a theoretical known amount of dissolved carbonate for respectively pH = 5.2 and 7. pH = 7 gives the most precise result with a deviations on less than 4%.

Important improvements for the analyse method:

- Heating to the boiling point for better precipitation when adding BaCl₂.
- Heating after adding HCl to prevent the undesired reaction:

- pH as indicator instead of methyl red.
- pH = 7 gives a better precision than pH = 5.2.
- Auto titration attain the pH value more precise than a manual titration.

Model

Other¹ have develop a model to describe the CO₂-loading and temperature profiles in the column. The model is modified to the specific column, and tested to see the accuracy. In general there are good correlations between the model and the experiments, but the model does not take into account that the heat capacity of the liquid changes as a function of CO₂-loading. This error becomes more vital as the loading increases. The model predicts the concentration in the gas outlet quite well, and is thereby able to approximate the absorption efficiency.

Fig. 2. Simulation plotted together with the experimental values. The air flows is 580 l/min with 9.5% CO₂. Liquid flow 2.1 l/min

Results

Removal efficiency as a function of absorption height

The CO₂ removal efficiency (CO₂ removed from the gas) is tested for different absorption heights varied from 2 to 10m while the MEA-liquid flow is kept constant. From an absorption height of 4m to 8m the efficiency varies in a range from 80-100%. To remove the last 10% of CO₂ it will require a lot more absorption height, making it very expensive. The temperature and the loading does not depend much on the absorption height.

Fig. 4. The absorption efficiency as a function of height for a number of liquid flows. The gas flow is 580 l/min with a CO₂ concentration of 10% and 90% N₂. The liquid flows varied from 2.1-9.0 l/min.

Fig. 5. The loading-, temperature- and the gas concentration profile with the conditions: Gas flow of 580 l/min (9.5% CO₂), liquid flow of 4.2 l/min and a lean load of 0.11 mole CO₂/mole MEA.

Removal efficiency as a function of liquid flow

A certain height is fixed and then the CO₂ removal efficiencies are plotted for different liquid flows. At low absorption heights the liquid flow matters a lot, while it is not the case at higher absorption heights. The temperature and loading depends heavily on the liquid flows (see fig. 7 and 8). The maximum values reached are ΔT=33°C and a change in loading of 0.21 mole CO₂/mole MEA. It has not been possible to reach the theoretical max loading of 0.50 mole/mole in any of the experiments.

Fig. 6. Absorption efficiency as a function of liquid flow rates. The gas flow is constant (580 l/min, 10% CO₂ and 90% N₂).

Fig. 7. Gas concentration-, temperature- and loading profile with a liquid flow of 8.9 l/min. The absorption height is 10m and the rich MEA loading is 0.163mole CO₂/mole MEA.

Fig. 8. Gas concentration-, temperature- and loading profile with a liquid flow of 2.1 l/min. The absorption height is 6m and the rich MEA loading is 0.325 mole CO₂/mole MEA.

Removal efficiency as a function of lean loading

The reaction and diffusion rates depends on the loading of MEA, therefore it is important to see how the plant perform, when the lean loading is far from clean when it enters the column. A number of experiments have been performed to cover this aspect. In fig. 9 it can be seen that a cleaner lean loading perform very aggressive in the beginning of the column, while a more loaded lean-MEA has a more constant removal throughout the column.

Fig. 9. Different lean loadings. Constant gas and liquid flow (gas flow: 580 l/min (10% CO₂), liquid flow: 4.2 l/min).

Fig. 10. The CO₂ removal efficiency is decreasing for an increment in the lean loading.

Conclusion

- The analysis method has been improved significantly to yield ≤ 4% deviation.
- Good correlation between model and experiments, though some improvements on the temperature profile needs to be made.
- A comprehensive study on how the plant operates at different operations conditions.
- The optimal operation conditions will be a liquid flow of 2.1 l/min and with a column height of 6m, which will remove more than 90% of the CO₂